

STUDY OF THE EFFICIENCY OF A CATALYTIC CONVERTER AND REDUCTION OF TOXICITY OF CAR ENGINE OUTPUT GASES

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Abstract. *The purpose of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of a catalytic converter used to reduce the toxicity of exhaust gases from an automobile engine. The research will study the effect of various factors (temperature, fuel composition, engine operating mode) on the effectiveness of exhaust gas purification using a converter. In particular, the number of harmful substances such as carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and hydrocarbons (HC), as well as the changes that occur in exhaust gases before and after purification by a catalyst, will be analyzed. The results of the study are expected to help identify the most effective methods of reducing emissions and improve the air quality of large cities through the development of environmentally friendly technologies.*

Keywords: *catalytic converter, nitrogen oxides, hydrocarbon, carbon oxides, exhaust gas.*

At present, the most important indicators determining the perfection of piston engines for various purposes are considered to be the characteristics of exhaust gas toxicity and fuel efficiency, which largely determine the prospects for further improvement and use of automobile engines. Automobile and tractor engines pollute the atmosphere with harmful substances emitted with exhaust and crankcase gases, as well as fuel vapors from tanks.

This article presents results for reducing the toxicity of exhaust gases of an automobile engine using secondary air supply systems to optimize the operation of the neutralizer in engine start-up and warm-up modes.

The experiment was conducted in the department's laboratory "Internal combustion engines, refrigeration and cryogenic equipment" (Fig. 1) at TSTU in Tashkent, and assessed the toxicity of exhaust gases (EG) of automobile engines L2C grade (Table 1) and the efficiency of the three-way catalytic converter.

At the same time, 95...99% of harmful emissions from modern automobile engines come from exhaust gases, which are a complex aerosol, the composition of which is determined by the engine operating mode, combustion of fuel, excess air, various micro-impurities (gaseous, liquid and solid particles entering the exhaust system from the engine cylinders).

In practice, EGs contain products of incomplete combustion of fuel: carbon monoxide CO, hydrocarbons CH, aldehydes, solid carbon particles (soot), peroxide compounds, hydrogen and excess oxygen, products of thermal reactions of the interaction of nitrogen with oxygen (nitrogen oxides NO_x), inorganic compounds of certain substances present in the fuel (sulfur dioxide, metal compounds, etc.).

In total, up to 290 different components can be found in exhaust gases, which are divided into several groups (Table 3): - a group of non-toxic substances (nitrogen, oxygen, hydrogen, water vapor, carbon dioxide); - a group of toxic substances (carbon monoxide CO, nitrogen oxides NO_x,

hydrocarbons CH (paraffins, olefins, aromatics, etc.), aldehydes R_xCHO, soot). Table 2 presents the sources of formation of toxic substances emitted by a car engine.

Fig. 1. Laboratory test bench

Table 1. Engine L2C technical specifications

Engine capacity, cc	1485
Maximum power, hp	105 - 106
Maximum torque, Nm (kgm) at rpm .	134 (14) / 4000
Fuel used: gasoline	Gasoline AI-92
Fuel consumption, l/100 km	6.7 - 7.6
Engine type	In-line, 4-cylinder
Maximum power, hp (kW) at rpm.	105 (77) / 5800 106 (78) / 5800
Compression ratio	10.2
Cylinder diameter, mm	74.7
Piston stroke, mm	84.7
Number of valves per cylinder	4

Table 2. Sources of toxic substances formation

EMISSION SOURCES, %	CO	CH	NO _x
EXHAUST GASES	95	55	98
CRANKCASE GASES	5	5	2
EVAPORATION OF FUEL FROM TANKS	0	40	0

Atmospheric air acts as a fuel oxidizer and consists mainly of nitrogen ($\approx 79\%$) and oxygen ($\approx 21\%$). Ideally, with a stoichiometric mixture of hydrocarbon fuel and air, the combustion products should contain only nitrogen N₂, carbon dioxide CO₂ and water H₂O. Exhaust gases are a mixture of gaseous products.

Table 3. Content of various substances in OG

OG component	Content by volume, %		Note
	gasoline engines	diesels	
Nitrogen N ₂	74...77	76 ... 78	Non-toxic
Oxygen O ₂	0.3...0.8	2 ... 18	Non-toxic
Water H ₂ O	3.0...5.5	0.5 ... 4.0	Non-toxic
Carbon dioxide CO ₂	5...12	1...10	Non-toxic
Carbon monoxide CO	0.1...10	0, 01...0,5	Toxic
Nitrogen oxides NO _x	0.1...0.5	0, 001...0,4	Toxic
Hydrocarbons CH	2-3	0, 01 ... 1, 1	Toxic
Aldehydes R _x CHO	up to 0.2	0, 01 ... 0, 09	Toxic
Sulfur oxide SO ₂	up to 0.002	up to 0.03	Toxic
Soot, g/m ³	0.04	0.01...1.1	Toxic
Benz (a) pyrene	up to 0.02	up to 0.01	Carcinogenic

An analysis of the composition of EG of petrol engines and diesel engines confirmed that EG of petrol engines is currently more dangerous. Research shows that a petrol engine emits carbon monoxide CO approximately seven times more and aldehydes three times more than a diesel engine. However, EG of diesel engines also contains a large number of toxic products of incomplete combustion of fuel (carbon monoxide, hydrocarbons, soot).

Emissions of toxic components of exhaust gases depend significantly on the operating mode of the automobile engine. Table 4 presents the values of emitted toxic components in relative units at various operating modes of the automobile engine.

Fuel vapors (CH) - vapors from fuel tanks, elements of engine fuel supply systems (joints, hoses, etc.), containing hydrocarbons of various compositions. Crankcase gases - a mixture of gases penetrating through the gaps between the piston rings and the cylinder from the combustion chamber into the engine crankcase, as well as oil vapors located in the crankcase. Crankcase gases must be diverted through the crankcase ventilation system to the engine intake and then burned in the cylinder.

The Euro environmental standard is a document that regulates the content of harmful substances in the exhaust gases of vehicles, and also provides for the release into circulation of motor gasoline and diesel fuel of the Euro 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 standards. Let us consider in more detail the development of this standard. Vehicle tests for compliance with the standards are carried

out according to special standards that provide for certain technologies for measuring the emissions of toxic components by vehicle engines.

Table 4. Toxic substances emitted from engine exhaust gases in various vehicle operating modes, %

Component OG	Vehicle operating modes			
	Idle move	Constant speed	Acceleration from 0 to 40 km/h	Slowdown from 40 to 0 km/h
Carbon monoxide genus CO	0.5...8.5	0.3...3.5	2.5...5	1.8...4.5
Hydrocarbons SN	0.03...0.12	0.02...0.6	0.12...0.17	0.23...0.44
Nitrogen oxides NO _x	0.005...0.01	0.1...0.2	0.12...0.19	0.003...0.005

These tests are conducted on special running drums. Running drums allow simulating the movement of a car on the road right in the box. The nature of the car's operating modes on running drums is determined by the so-called driving cycle, which is a certain combination of acceleration, braking, stops (idling), engine starts at appropriate time intervals. The car's operating modes according to the driving cycle are selected in such a way that they simulate the movement of a car in urban conditions and on the highway. In addition, there are "cold" and "hot" driving cycles (with starting and warming up a cold engine and one heated to operating temperatures).

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of the design of a three-component catalytic converter:
 1 – steel body; 2 – heat-resistant damping substrate; 3 – ceramic matrix (block); 4 – ceramics;
 5 – intermediate layer; 6 – catalytically active layer

During the process of creating automobiles, such tests are carried out independently by the factories that manufacture automobile equipment. It should be noted that in Euro standards toxic emissions are measured in grams per kilometre (g/km) of vehicle travel.

Standards for tractor diesel engines (as well as other similar equipment) provide for the measurement of toxic emissions in grams per kilowatt-hour, which allows determining the standardized toxicity of EG on engine stands. To reduce the toxicity of EG to the values standardized by the standards, three-component catalytic converters (CC) are used.

Their task is to convert toxic components of exhaust gases (CO, CH, NO_x) into harmless components (water vapor H₂O, carbon dioxide CO₂, nitrogen N₂). In diesel engines and engines with direct gasoline injection, a particulate filter is usually used together with the CF. Structurally, a typical KN (Fig. 2) consists of a steel housing in which a ceramic matrix (block) is placed, having many small longitudinal channels of rectangular cross-section (cross-section size from 0.3 to 1 mm) with a developed internal surface, increasing the contact area of the exhaust gas with the catalytic layer.

Fig. 3. – Schematic diagram of the secondary air supply system

1. Air filter; 2. Supercharger housing; 3. Turbine; 4. Compressor; 5. Neutralizer; 6. Inlet manifold; 7. Air flow sensor; 8. ICE; 9. Exhaust manifold; 10. Electropneumatic valve; 11. Throttle valve

The matrix is made using a special technology from heat-resistant ceramics (cordierite), which is also resistant to thermal shocks. The normal operating temperature of the ceramic matrix is 300...800 °C. Short-term operation of the neutralizer at a temperature of 800...1000 °C is allowed. At temperatures above 1000 °C, the ceramics begin to soften, and at $t \geq 1450$ °C, the matrix melts.

The catalytically active layer consists of noble metals - platinum Pt, rhodium Rh, ruthenium Ru, palladium Pd, etc. It is due to these metals, which have a catalytic effect, that toxic components of the exhaust gases are converted into harmless substances. A feature of the CN is a very narrow range of the highest efficiency of neutralization of toxic components (Fig. 2). This is due to the fact that for the most complete conversion of toxic substances, a balance between oxidation and reduction reactions is necessary, which can only be achieved with a stoichiometric composition of the fuel assembly, i.e. with $\alpha = 1.0$.

It is to maintain the fuel-air mixture composition at the level of $\alpha \approx 1.0$ that a λ -probe is used in the fuel supply control feedback loop in the gasoline engine control system. Thus, the most efficient operation of the CN is in a narrow range of fuel-air mixture compositions close to $\alpha = 1.0$

(the so-called λ -window). Efficiency E_i the effect of KN, %, for each of the neutralized toxic components of OG is determined by the formula

$$E_i = (K_{iin} - K_{iout}) / K_{iex}$$

where K_{iex} is the concentration of the i -th harmful substance at the inlet of the CN; K_{iout} is the concentration of the i -th harmful substance at the outlet of the CN. To determine the total (overall) efficiency of E_{Σ} neutralizer, it is necessary to multiply the calculated efficiency for each of the components - E_{CO} , E_{CH} , E_{NOx} . In practice, the total efficiency of a modern three-component neutralizer in certain modes can reach 95...98%. Thus, by determining the concentration of emissions of toxic components before and after a three-component neutralizer, it is possible to calculate the efficiency of the neutralizer for each component and its total efficiency.

Table 5. Technologies for determining toxic components in exhaust gases

Component to be determined	Determination technology
Carbon monoxide CO, carbon dioxide CO ₂	Non-dispersive infrared analyzer (NDIR)
Nitrogen oxides NO _x	Chemiluminescence detector (CLD)
General content hydrocarbons C _n H _m	Flame Ionization Detector (FID)
Individual hydrocarbons CH ₄	Combination of Gas Chromatography and Flame Ionization Detector (GC FID)
Individual hydrocarbons CH ₃ OH, CH ₂ O	Combination of impeller or cartridge filter and chromatographic analysis
Solid particles	1. Gravimetric method: weighing particulate filters before and after road tests 2. Counting the number of solid particles

Naturally, the efficiency of the neutralizer will change depending on the engine operating mode (composition of the fuel-air mixture). Therefore, it is more rational to determine the efficiency of the neutralizer not at one point, but by some characteristic. There are a large number of specialized devices for measuring toxic emissions in laboratory conditions - multi-component gas analyzers and smoke meters. They can operate on various principles (combinations of principles), which are presented in Table 5.

As a result of the work performed, an assessment was made of the possibility of using a secondary air supply system to optimize the operation of the neutralizer in engine start-up and warm-up modes. The following tasks were solved:

- the current level of technology on this issue was analyzed;
- various options for solving the problem were analyzed;
- the necessary calculations were carried out to evaluate the secondary air supply system;
- reduce the content of harmful impurities, lower the toxicity of exhaust gases, increase the efficiency of neutralizing toxic impurities in the exhaust gases of internal combustion engines.

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